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The Necessity of Building Higher Education Students' Competencies for Responsible Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Nigeria

¹Ojokheta, K.O. *PhD, MNAE* & ²Afolabi, Ifeoma Patricia

Department of Adult Education
University of Ibadan, Nigeria
E-mail: ko.ojokheta@gmail.com; ko.ojokheta@mail.ui.edu.ng
Tel Nos: 07033809512, 08028953529
ORCID iD: 0009-0006-5532-4813

Postgraduate Student, Department of Adult Education
University of Ibadan, Nigeria
Email: patfolab@yahoo.com
Tel No: 07059595585

ABSTRACT

This paper discussed the urgent need by management of higher education institutions in Nigeria to build students' competencies on responsible use of artificial intelligence (AI) and generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tools for learning. The paper was premised on the fear expressed by some scholars that the increasingly reliance of higher education students on AI and GenAI tools, which are prevalent online, to generate texts and assignments that are plausibly human can kill their critical thinking and research skills as well as encourage cheating and plagiarism. The paper began with a discussion of the origin, definitions, and dimensions of AI and GenAI. It further discussed the goals and advantages of using AI in education, the dangers in the use of AI and GenAI tools in education and research by students, and the contents of UNESCO's publications on "*Guidance for generative AI in education and research*", "*Guidance for policy-makers on AI and Education*" and the "*AI competency framework for students*". The paper also discussed the justifications for building higher education students competencies for responsible use of artificial intelligence in Nigeria and recommended the strategies that management of higher education institutions can adopt to achieve this task. The paper concluded that the implementation of the recommended strategies by management of higher education institutions will go a long way in helping higher education students to develop the skills for responsible use of AI and GenAI tools for learning.

Keywords: Higher education institutions, higher education students, competencies, responsible use of AI and GenAI tools

INTRODUCTION

The rapid iterations, proliferation, and application of artificial intelligence across all aspects of life and all sectors of human activities has made the world of today to be regarded as an artificial intelligence (AI) driven world. In recognition of this, governments all over the world, at the International Conference on Artificial

Intelligence and Education held in Beijing, China from 16 to 18 May 2019, the *Beijing Consensus on AI and Education*, acknowledged the urgent need for countries to develop AI literacy and more advanced AI competencies in people. The Beijing Consensus overwhelmingly agreed that Artificial Intelligence (AI) has the potential of reshaping the core foundations of teaching, learning and research (UNESCO, 2019) and also the potential to address some of the biggest challenges in education today, innovate teaching and learning practices, and ultimately accelerate the progress towards Sustainable Development Goal 4. It was in this context that Beijing Consensus underlined the need to equip people with AI literacy across all layers of society.

In Nigeria, higher education institutions have been in forefront of advancing AI through research and development with more AI research studies from academics in higher education institutions. Similarly, higher education students constitute one of the most dominant population that are more likely to use AI-tools to write assignments given in class, assignments at the end of the class, undergraduate long essays, postgraduate dissertations, and doctoral theses. The online prevalence of AI tools, designed to produce texts that are plausibly human to generate papers or texts and powered by Large Language Models (LLMs) including ChatGPT released in November 2022, are being relied upon by students in higher education institutions all over the world. This is becoming a cause for concern from scholars in the academic world. For example, Johnson, (2023) and Yang, (2023) have contended that there will always be the risk of both false positives and false negatives when tools are used to determine whether the texts were produced by a human or by an LLM. In view of this, there has been calls towards banning the use of ChatGPT and other similar tools across the world because of the belief that these tools kill critical thinking and research skills in students and encourage cheating and plagiarism among them (Johnson, 2023; Yang, 2023).

These expressed concerns have accelerated the necessity of building higher education students' competencies on the responsible and ethical use of AI across the world. It is in this regard that this paper was written advocating the urgent need for management of higher education institutions in Nigeria to develop strategic modalities for building higher education students' competencies for responsible use of AI. It further discussed the justifications and potential strategies for the achievement of this advocacy.

Origin, Definitions, and Dimensions AI and GenAI

Artificial intelligence (AI) is one of the most sophisticated technologies, including Robotics, Web3, Blockchain, Cloud computing, Quantum computing, Internet of Things (IoT), 3D Printing, Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality, and Biotechnology, that emerged in the fourth industrial revolution (4IR) and has become the most talked-about and widely used in human activities and endeavours (Ojokheta & Omokhabi, 2023). The field of AI was founded as an academic discipline at a workshop held on the campus of Dartmouth College, USA during the summer of 1956 and the attendees, who subsequently became the leaders of AI research for decades, predicted that a machine as intelligent as a human being would exist in no more than a generation (Moor, 2006). Artificial intelligence describes computers that can 'think' like humans and can recognise complex patterns, process information, draw conclusions, and make recommendations (Zhang, Zhang, & Li, 2019). For a given set of human-defined objectives, AI can make predictions, recommendations or decisions influencing real or virtual environments (Vincent-Lancrin & van der Vlies, 2020). They can perform many tasks that require human intelligence (Rossi, 2019).

Artificial intelligence is a field of computer science and technology that focuses on creating machines, systems, or software programmes capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence. These tasks include reasoning, learning, problem-solving, perception, understanding natural language, and making decisions. AI systems are designed to stimulate or replicate human cognitive functions and adapt to new information and situations. In other words, AI is a commonly used term to describe machines performing human-like cognitive functions like learning, understanding, reasoning, and interacting (Baruffaldi, Beuzekom, Dennis, Harhoff, Rao, Rosenfeld, & Squicciarini, 2020). UNESCO (2023) interprets AI broadly as systems with the ability to process data in a way which resembles intelligent behaviour.

Vincent-Lancrin and van der Vlies (2020) classified the types or dimensions of AI into seven categories:

1. Artificial Narrow Intelligence – This refers to AI designed to complete specific actions and it is unable to independently learn.

2. Artificial General Intelligence – This refers to AI designed to learn, think and perform at similar levels to humans.
3. Artificial Super-intelligence – This refers to AI which is able to surpass the knowledge and capabilities of humans.
4. Reactive Machines – This refers to AI capable of responding to external stimuli in real time but unable to build memory or store information for future.
5. Limited Memory AI – This refers to AI that can store knowledge and use it to learn and train for future tasks.
6. Theory of Mind AI – This refers to AI that can sense and respond to human emotions and perform the task of limited memory machines.
7. Self- Aware AI – This refers to AI that can recognize other’s emotions and has sense of self and human intelligence.

Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) was brought to global knowledge in late 2022 with the launch of ChatGPT (Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer), a chatbot developed by OpenAI and launched on 30 November, 2022, and has become the fastest growing app in history (Giannini, 2023). GenAI applications, including ChatGPT, has the power to imitate human capabilities to produce outputs such as texts, videos, music and software codes. GenAI refers to artificial intelligence systems capable of generating new content, such as text, images, music, or other forms of media, based on learned patterns from existing data. The technology utilises advanced algorithms like neural networks to understand and replicate complex patterns and structures. In other words, GenAI is often used to automatically generate content in response to prompts written in natural-language conversational interfaces and produces new content by drawing on existing content in webpages (UNESCO, 2023). The content can appear in texts written in natural language, images (including photographs, digital painting and cartoons), videos, music, and software code. GenAI is trained in using data collected from webpages, from social media conversations, and from other online media to generate its content by statistically analysing the distribution of words or other elements in the data it has ingested to identify and repeat common patterns of words which typically follow from other words (Anders, 2023).

Artificial Intelligence in Education: Concept, Promotion and Advantages

Globally, AI has become the new trend of technology in the education sector and competitively changing learning environment (Commonwealth of Learning [CoL], 2023). Artificial intelligence (AI) in education refers to the use of computers that mimic human perception and decision making to complete a task in the classroom and management of the class as well as the course load (Thompson, 2022). The goal of AI in education is to improve students learning and offload administrative tasks that take up teacher time. Realising the importance of AI in education, UNESCO in 2019 organised two international conferences on the use of AI in education. The theme of the first conference entitled "*Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Development*" examined the potential benefits and drawbacks of using AI in education with over 40 AI initiatives presented and evaluated the takeaways from different national policies and strategies that used AI to help fulfil Sustainable Development Goal 4 [SDG 4] (UNESCO, 2019). The second UNESCO conference, with the theme "*Artificial Intelligence and Education: Planning Education in the AI Era: Lead and Leap*", sought to advance global collaboration and alliances to support the egalitarian, inclusive, and open application of AI in education and thus provided participants the opportunity to discuss the most recent advancements in AI and how they affected teaching and learning. A document, entitled "*Beijing Consensus on Artificial Intelligence and Education*," which served as a call to action for UNESCO Member States to advance the integration and application of AI in education, was produced at the conference.

The advantages of AI in education has been documented in literature. For example, UNESCO (2019) documented the advantages of the application of AI in education as follows:

- Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems can transformed classrooms by allowing students from any country to access education, regardless of their preferred language of instruction or any potential visual or auditory limitations.

- Learners can get real-time subtitles for all the teacher's instructions and lectures with AI-powered tools like Presentation Translator.
- Additionally, AI makes it possible for personalised learning which adapts the educational process to each student's unique interests and history.
- AI makes sure that students have the most efficient and customised learning experience by adapting to their level of expertise, rate of learning, and desired goals.
- AI software can also reduce costs by streamlining the course development process and producing interactive content more quickly. As a result, teachers are better able to address any area where students may be having difficulty.

In a follow-up view to the above, Liu, Saleh, & Huang, (2021) also listed, among others, the importance of using AI for education thus:

- AI helps teachers spot gaps in lectures and educational materials.
- It also provides customised messages with tips for the right response to teachers when students submit erroneous responses to homework assignments.
- AI is also useful for automating non-teaching tasks including attendance monitoring, organising teaching resources, grading assignments, handling paperwork, creating progress reports, and maintaining teaching materials at lower educational institutions (primary and secondary schools).
- Teachers can spend less time on non-teaching duties which frequently take up a large portion of their time through the automation of these duties with AI and spend more time imparting crucial competencies to students.
- AI in education can assist students with tutoring using Chatbots and AI tutors, especially in disciplines that may be taught successfully online when teachers are not present. AI also makes it easier to create intelligent material, such as online manuals, textbooks, movies, and other educational devices.

Despite the importance of using AI in education, it also possesses inherent dangers which higher education students must be aware of.

The Dangers in the Use of AI Tools Including (GenAI) by Students

Higher education students' in Nigeria need to be aware and have more knowledge of the many dangers associated with the use of AI tools including ChatGPT and other Large Language Models (LLMs). Some of these dangers include:

1. **Inability of AI tools to generate solutions to real-world challenges** - Even though AI can produce new content, it cannot generate new ideas or solutions to real-world challenges since it does not understand real-world objects or social relations than underpin language.
2. **AI cannot be trusted to be accurate.** For example, while GenAI tools like ChatGPT can often generate answers that sound reasonable, they cannot be relied upon to be accurate (OpenAI, 2023).
3. **Integrity concerns from the utilisation of AI technology** – AI is a technology that learns from existing systems. If data from the existing systems which AI learns from is biased, the output from AI will show biases. Therefore, students' learning through the AI system will assimilate the bias without knowing about it (Sharma, 2023).
4. **Security and privacy concerns** – AI systems need access to huge amounts of data to generate content. However, if there are data breaches and unauthorised access to such data, this will result in threats to security and privacy of such data. Invariably, such data are either comprised or jeopardised (Sharma, 2023).
5. **Elimination of the human factor in the educational landscape** – AI often leads to the provision of customised teaching and learning solution through automation. Therefore, over-reliance on it can lead to elimination of the human factor in the educational landscape which prevents real-time interaction between the teacher and the learners. Real-time interaction between the teacher and learners is inevitable in educational transactions. In essence, AI must never be over-relied upon to replace teacher-learner interaction and relationship because teachers cannot be displaced by machine (UNESCO, 2019).

6. **AI-assisted approach for writing papers or texts cannot be relied upon** – AI-assisted approach for writing academic papers, texts, or articles cannot be absolutely relied upon by higher education students. This is usually noticeable in the references cited. For example, in a study conducted to find-out if ChatGPT could be used to assist in writing credible, peer-reviewed, and scientific review articles, Kacena, Plotkin, and Fehrenbacher (2023) reported that 70% of the references cited were found inaccurate.
7. **AI-assisted approach can result in higher likelihood of plagiarism** – Since AI-assisted approach generate content from huge amounts of data it has access to, such generated content may result in high similarity index in comparison with papers or articles in related areas. Invariably, papers or articles written through AI-approach may show higher likelihood of plagiarism (Kacena, Plotkin, & Fehrenbacher, 2023).
8. **AI-assisted approach can help students to cheat** – When ChatGPT was first launched, educators across the world expressed concerns about its potential to generate essays and how it might help students to cheat (Anders, 2023). This concern has not substantially changed among some educators since the internet is now awash with suggestions for the use of AI, especially ChatGPT, in learning and research. For example, a smart student can ask ChatGPT to generate a write-up for an assignment given in class and submit the generated write-up without any additional input from such student. This process does not only constitute cheating but also kills critical thinking, analysis, and skills in such student (Ojokheta, K. O. & Odusanya, Olatunbosun, S. E, 2024).

Similarly, UNESCO (2023) has concisely compiled and published the dangers in the application and use of GenAI systems in education and research to include the following:

1. **Use of content without consent** – GenAI models are built from large amount of data from texts, sounds, codes and images usually scraped from the internet without any owner’s permission. Consequently, GenAI tools most times violate the intellectual property rights. Therefore, to curb the violation of these rights, students’ must be aware of the rights of data owners and must check whether the GenAI tools they are using violate any existing regulations.
2. **Unexplainable models used to generate outputs** – Artificial neural networks (ANNs) used to generate outputs in GenAI are considered as ‘*black boxes*’ because their inner workings are not open to inspection. Therefore, ANNs are not ‘transparent’ or ‘explainable’ and it is not possible to ascertain how their generated outputs are determined. Invariably, it is difficult to know how and why a particular content has been created or generated by GenAI system.
3. **GenAI encourages plagiarism to a greater extent** – GenAI encourages plagiarism among students in higher education institutions. For example, GenAI might allow students to pass off texts and write-ups that they didn’t write as their own work. This is simply plagiarism.
4. **Pollution of AI-generated contents in the internet** – Materials generated by GenAI can appear to be quite accurate and convincing; however, they often contain errors, biased ideas, and harmful statements (Bender, Gebru, McMillan-Major, & Shmitchell, 2021). Unfortunately, these polluted materials are increasingly being spread throughout the internet for most learners across the world. This poses high risk for students’ who do not know the source of the content or have strong prior knowledge of the topic in question. Therefore, to curb the spread of polluted materials, higher education students must be made aware that GenAI systems are capable of spreading offensive and unethical materials.
5. **ChatGPTs do not understand the real world** – ChatGPTs only repeat language patterns found in their training data usually drawn from the internet, starting with random patterns, without understanding their meaning. This is why ChatGPTs are likened to a parrot who can mimic sounds without actually comprehending what they are saying. It is in this context that ChatGPTs are pejoratively referred to as “*stochastic parrots*” (Bender, Gebru, McMillan-Major, & Shmitchell, 2021). GenAI is not informed by observations of the real world or other key aspects of the scientific method. It doesn’t also align with human and social values. As a result, GenAI cannot genuinely generate new content about the real world. In essence, generation of content by GenAI is merely a conjecture.

6. **Incorrect generation of texts** – As stated above, GenAI models, including ChatGPT, can produce texts/materials that appear accurate and convincing but such texts can contain errors, biased ideas, and harmful statement. This is because GenAI systems only repeat language patterns found in their training data usually texts drawn from the internet. Generally, GenAI cannot genuinely generate new and original content about the real world. GenAI doesn't understand anything and the text it generates can be incorrect. Therefore, students' must be extra careful in using GenAI tools, especially ChatGPT, in generating texts and materials.
7. **Limitation of diversity of opinions** – GenAI tools, including ChatGPT, produce output or answer to any required question or topic based on the values of the owners and creators of the data used to train such tools. The frequency of the words in the training data of such tools is more likely to be repeated in its output or answer. This leads to limitation of plural opinions and expression of ideas. Therefore, students' must be made aware that any content they get or share on the internet is a reflection of the creator's imputed data and not a reflection of plural opinions or ideas which could have been manipulated.
8. **Generation of fake images** – GenAI systems, including ChatGPT, can be used to alter or manipulate existing images and videos to generate fake ones that are difficult to distinguish from real ones. Thus, GenAI is making it increasingly possible and easy to create fake images, videos, news, and incorporation of people's faces into something entirely fake without their knowledge or consent. GenAI can also be used to spread disinformation, misinformation and hate speech. This is unethical, immoral and criminal act. Therefore, students' must be made aware that any content they get or share on the internet might have been manipulated and used in unethical ways.
9. **Massive digital poverty** – GenAI relies upon huge amounts of data and massive computing power and these data are highly essential for the economic development of countries and for the digital opportunities of individuals. However, those countries and people who do not have access to or cannot afford enough data are left in a situation of 'data poverty' (Marwala, 2023). For example, the powerhouse of AI, in terms of generation and processing of data, are largely concentrated in those technologically advanced countries located in the Global North. Invariably, GenAI models, including ChatGPT, are trained with data which reflect the values and norms of the Global North.
10. **Limited regulatory control and governance of GenAI** – It is globally known that GenAI may augment human capacities in completing certain tasks; however, there is limited democratic control of the companies that are promoting GenAI (UNESCO, 2024). This has led to the issue of regulation particularly in access to and use of domestic data generated on a country's territory.

To overcome the above-discussed dangers associated with the application and use of GenAI in education, UNESCO (2022) published a document entitled "*Guidance for generative AI in education and research*". The publication noted that China is the only country reported to have released specific official regulations on GenAI as at July 2023 (UNESCO, 2023); less than 10 percent of schools and universities, out of 450 schools and universities globally surveyed by UNESCO, had institutional policies or formal guidance concerning the use of generative AI applications (UNESCO, 2023), and the established fact that the internet is now awash with suggestions for the use of GenAI by students' in education and research to inspire new ideas, generate multi-perspective examples, develop learning plans, summarise existing materials, and stimulate image creation (UNESCO, 2023). The publication, therefore, calls on governments of UNESCO Member States to regulate the use of GenAI in schools and in education generally to ensure a human-centred approach and the planning of appropriate regulations, policies and human capacity development to ensure that GenAI becomes a tool that genuinely benefits and empowers teachers, learners and researchers (The UNESCO Courier, 2023).

Justifications for Building Higher Education Students Competencies for Responsible Use of Artificial Intelligence in Nigeria

Since there is the high possibility of students in higher education institutions in Nigeria to rely on AI to generate papers, long essays, dissertations, and theses for submission, it becomes a matter of urgency for higher education institutions in Nigeria to develop a strategic framework for responsible use of AI and GenAI in learning and researches arising from the following:

1. The need for responsible use of AI by higher education students – Higher education students are highly vast and more active in knowledge and utilisation of digital technologies for various purposes. This is evident in the various contents, videos, and images generated and posted in social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, among others. With the unrestricted and unregulated use of digital technologies by these students, it is easier for them to engage in unethical and irresponsible use of AI. This is also becoming noticeable in the use of AI to generate clown voices, manipulate and create existing images, news, and videos that are difficult to distinguish from real ones, incorporate people’s faces into something entirely fake without their knowledge or consent, and spread disinformation, misinformation and hate speech. To prevent these irresponsible uses of AI, higher education students’ competencies must be built for responsible use of AI in Nigeria.

2. The danger and limitations of AI in learning and research – As good as AI is in learning and research, higher education students’ must, however, be aware and have more knowledge in the dangers and limitations of AI for learning and research as discussed above.

3. Knowledge of prominent AI tools for generating papers, texts and contents - Students’ must be aware and have more knowledge of the existence of numerous AI tools online which are often advertised as impeccable in generating written texts. Some of the most prominent intelligent AI assistants include:

- **Meta AI** (Seen as capable of complex reasoning, following instructions, visualising ideas, and solving problems).
- **Writely AI** (Seen as helping students’ to refine their writing skills and develop stronger communication abilities with its provision of real-time suggestions for improving grammar, style, and clarity as well as the for improvement and suggestion of alternative wording to enhance the overall quality of written work).
- **Grammarly AI** (Seen as helping students’ to ensure not only accuracy in spelling, punctuation, and grammar in their written works but also in producing clear, compelling, and easy to read works by flagging potential issues in a text and make context-specific suggestions to help with grammar, spelling and usage, wordiness, style, punctuation, tone, and even plagiarism).
- **ChatGPT AI** (Seen as having the power to imitate human capabilities to produce outputs such as texts, videos, music and software codes and helping students’ to elicit responses to any demands on learning including writing of papers or articles, editing papers, creation of study notes, creation of teaching assistance mechanisms, creation of research outlines and outcomes, among others).

While these AI tools possess these features, students’ competence to use them responsibly must be built since they inadvertently create works that lack authenticity and possibility of plagiarism.

4. AI cannot replace real-time teacher-learner interaction and relationship - Even though AI produces customised teaching and learning solution through automation, higher education students’ must be aware and have more knowledge that attendance in classes cannot be avoided since AI cannot be relied upon to replace real-time teacher-learner interaction and relationship.

5. AI cannot generate new and accurate ideas or solutions to real-world challenges - Students’ must be made aware and have more knowledge that even though AI can generate or produce new content, such content cannot be relied upon to be accurate.

6. AI-assisted approach for writing papers cannot be absolutely relied upon - Students’ must be aware and have more knowledge that even though AI generated papers cannot be absolutely relied upon in the references cited. This was ascertained by Kacena, Plotkin, and Fehrenbacher (2023) who reported that 70% of the references cited in ChatGPT assisted academic articles/papers were found inaccurate.

7. Assimilation of bias without knowing it - Students' must aware and have more knowledge that the assimilation of bias is often high without them knowing if data from the AI system is compromised. For example, if the AI system is biased, there is high possibility that data may be compromised or jeopardised if there are data breaches and unauthorised access to such data (Sharma, 2023).

8. Higher likelihood of plagiarism in AI generated papers - The rise and proliferation of AI engines, such as ChatGPT, makes inputting requests such as creating an essay and receiving an output of a fully loaded generic essays more accessible to students. Therefore, students' must be aware and have more knowledge that there is the likelihood of plagiarism from AI generic essays or papers. They must also be aware of the existence of tools for detecting plagiarised works and the consequences they are likely to face if found to have submitted plagiarised works. Plagiarism occurs when someone uses words, ideas, or work products attributable to another identifiable person or source without attributing the work to the source from which it was obtained (Fishman, 2016) and has been described as the '*scourge of academic life*' (Angelil-Carter, 2000), '*an academic felony*' (Laird, 2001) and '*the nemesis of originality*' (Sutherland-Smith 2005; 2008). Turnitin has become the most prominent commercial web-based text matching-software detection tool often used by management of higher education institutions in Nigeria to determine, in percentage score, the similarity index or the extent of the plagiarised works submitted by students against repositories and databases of periodicals, journals and other publications.

9. Higher possibility of students to engage in cheating with the use of AI tools - Some smart students use ChatGPT and other LLMs to generate texts for an assignment given in class and research projects. They thereafter, submit the generated texts and projects as if they are theirs without any input from them. This does not only amount to cheating but also kills critical thinking, analysis, and research skill in students.

10. Knowledge and understanding of the core ethics of using AI - Students' must also be aware and have more knowledge of the core ethics of using AI such as: the legitimate use of AI for the well-being of others without harming them, the right to privacy and data protection, the promotion of social justice, fairness, and non-discrimination to others, and the responsible and accountable use of AI to avoid conflicts with human norms and threats to environmental well-being, among others.

Recommended Strategies for Building Higher Education Students' Competency for Responsible Use of AI in Nigeria

In order to ensure responsible and ethical use of AI by students' in higher education institutions in Nigeria, the following recommendations are put-forward for management of such institutions to implement:

1. Development of policy, regulation and creative use of AI framework by each institution – Management of higher education institutions in Nigeria must urgently develop policy, regulation, and creative framework to guide students on responsible use of AI and GenAI while they are in the institution. Promotion of equitable and inclusive access of students to AI application and development of students' AI competencies including GenAI-related skills should be the key issues to be included in the policy framework. For regulatory framework, the key issues should include: development of institution's data protection regulation; establishment of guiding principles on responsible use of AI and GenAI by students' and establishment of copyright laws to regulate AI and GenAI-generated content by students'. For creative use, the key issues should include: control of the process of using AI and GenAI tools as well as provision of guidance and capacity building training of students about AI and GenAI tools.

2. Inclusion of the responsible use of AI in students' handbook – Management of higher education institutions in Nigeria should adequately ensure that the responsible use of AI and GenAI is included and comprehensively discussed in the undergraduate and postgraduate students' handbook to make them become aware and have deeper knowledge of how to use AI for their learning and research while they are in the institution.

3. Interactive session with students' on how AI is changing the education sector during the orientation programme - During the orientation programme usually organised for newly admitted students' upon resumption of studies in higher education institutions, management should ensure that an interactive session with students' on how AI is changing the education sector globally in terms of the potential opportunities and

advantages of using AI in the education sector as well as the challenges and potential drawbacks should be included in the orientation programme.

4. Capacity building training of higher education students to embrace AI responsibly – To complement the inclusion of the responsible use of AI in students' handbook, management of higher education institutions in Nigeria should, at the commencement of each academic session, organise practical capacity building training of students to embrace AI responsibly for learning and research.

5. Enhancing higher education students' knowledge on using AI in academic writing and research - Similarly, management of higher education institutions in Nigeria should organise capacity building workshop for higher education students, in the first semester after their admission to the institution, to equip them with the knowledge of the following: (1) how to use AI in academic writing and research, (2) the knowledge of the integration of generative AI to improve academic writing skills, and (3) the knowledge of AI writing software tools mostly advertised online. Students must be reminded that overuse of AI can make them to lose important skills such as critical thinking, analysis, and research skills. This will help enhance their understanding of the responsible use of these tools for writing of human generated projects, dissertations and theses rather than AI-generated contents.

6. Students' should be made aware that lecturers will detect submitted AI-generated Texts – If students' are aware that any submitted AI-generated text will be detected by their lecturers, they are more likely to refrain from engaging in such acts. It is highly important for lecturers to be vigilant about articles/papers submitted by students in this era of proliferated AI-generated texts. This is because it is quite challenging to detect such texts. Therefore, management of higher education institutions in Nigeria must organise on yearly basis, possibly at the commencement of a new academic session, a capacity building training of lecturers to equip them with the knowledge of how to detect AI generated texts submitted by students at both undergraduate and postgraduate programmes. The training programme should contain contents such as step -by-step guide of detecting automated AI-generated texts and the specialised online tools or AI-detection software that can be used to detect such texts.

7. Lecturers should constantly remind students' not to rely on automated AI-generated texts during classes – Management of higher education institutions in Nigeria should kindly request lecturers, through internal memorandum, to continuously remind and warn students during classes never to rely on automated AI-generated texts because of the inherent dangers discussed in this paper. Students' should also be reminded of the consequences of being caught for irresponsible use of AI especially the submission of automated AI-generated texts.

CONCLUSION

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) and GenAI in education and research in higher education is no doubt desirable in modern times. In order to prevent the irresponsible and unethical use of AI by students in higher education institutions in Nigeria, it becomes imperative for management of such institutions to build students' knowledge and competency for responsible and ethical use of AI and GenAI. The strategies that management of such institutions can adopt to build the students competency have been comprehensively discussed in this paper. It is hoped that these strategies will be extensively implemented by the management. More importantly, management of higher education institutions in Nigeria are urged to rely on the UNESCO's freely available online publications for the development of institutional policy, regulation, and creative use framework for responsible use of AI by students in higher education institutions in Nigeria. The publications are: the 2021 Recommendation on Ethics of Artificial Intelligence publication, the 2023 Guidance for Generative AI in Education and Research publication, the 2023 Guidance for Policy-Makers on AI and Education publication, and the 2024 AI competency framework for students.

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